

THE CONCEPT OF INVASIVE SPECIES IN NATURAL INSECT PEST ECOSYSTEMS AND IN ANTHROPOGENICALLY TRANSFORMED TERRITORIES

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ABSTRACT

The insect world is very widespread in nature and has a diverse structure, with species persistence and invasiveness observed in ecological habitats. Each species has its own structure and characteristics, today it is important to study their characteristics according to the degree of adaptation to the environment, their role in nature, beneficial and harmful aspects for humanity. Insects are an integral part of the habitat and are constantly adapting to the new environment they are in. Invasive species that have entered the environment due to various common abiotic, biotic, and anthropogenic factors also gradually develop adaptive characteristics for these territories.

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Biomaterials collected from the territory of lower Amudaryo biosphere reserve, where the species are most common in the research work, based on the feeding process of xylophage-insects *Populus afghanica* (Aitch.et Hemsb), *Quercus rubra* (L.), *Pinus silvestris* (L.), *Populus pruinosa* (Schrenk.), *Populus nigra* (L.), *Populus alba* (L.), *Salix alba* (L.), *Ulmus densa* (Litv.), *Tamarix hispida* (Willd.), *Elaeagnus angustifolia* (L.), *Haloxyton aphyllum* (Minkw.) are permanent, free-living, invasive and quarantine species studied The dominant species are *Xylocopa valga* - carpenter bee, *Buprestis rustica* - shiny beetle, *Hylotrupes bajulus* - black house mustache beetle, *Anobium pertinax* - house borer, *Anacanthotermes turkestanicus* - Turkestan termite, and *A.ahngerianus* - Caspian sea termite. *Anobium punctatum*, *Acmaeoderella* sp., *Buprestis rustica*, *Trachypteris picta*, *Melanophila picta*, and *Cratomerus intermedius* were recorded as invasive species (Zhuginisov et al., 2018; Ganieva et al., 2019).

Xylophagous insects are known to feed on various dried woody products derived from plant flora, and some species have adapted to feed on living plants. Often, invasive species spread widely into areas with natural ecosystems due to anthropogenic factors. In this case, xylophage-insects expand their range through human-made furniture and import and export construction materials based on wood products, resulting in the presence of quarantine species. Also, the role of the food factor is important in the distribution of insect species. For this reason, it is necessary to pay attention to every imported building material entering our republic, observing the quarantine rules.

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